

Learning in nature: An amplified human rights-based framework

Elena Tuparevska

Faculty of Psychology and Education, University of Deusto, Bilbao, Spain

Correspondence: Faculty of Psychology and Education, University of Deusto.

elena.tuparevska3@deusto.es.

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Human beings are spending less time in nature than previous generations. Without opportunities to interact with nature, we are unable to forge deeper connections with the natural world, leading to indifference and unwillingness to protect it. At the same time, climate change has led to biodiversity loss and new threats such as pandemics, making the issue of the disconnection between humans and nature even more pertinent. This article proposes a modified human rights-based framework to education that incorporates nature as an integral part. I draw on UNESCO's framework for the human rights-based approach to education which entails three distinct dimensions: access to education, educational quality, and educational environment. I argue that introducing nature as a crucial part of the educational environment can contribute to upholding both human rights and the fundamental rights of nature. By drawing on ecopedagogy and Indigenous beliefs underlining a harmonious relationship with nature, we can move away from the current anthropocentric approach and address the environmental crisis in a meaningful way.

Keywords: nature; education; rights-based approach; Indigenous beliefs; ecopedagogy.

Introduction

Human beings today are less likely to spend time in nature than previous generations. Urbanization and sedentary lifestyles are limiting both our access to nature and the time we have available to spend in nature. It is estimated that European citizens spend approximately 90% of their time indoors: at home, work, and school (WHO, 2014). Researchers and educators have been especially concerned about the growing disconnection between children and the natural world. With declining opportunities for free, unstructured play in nature, there has been an emergence of a phenomenon named by Richard Louv (2008), author of the book *Last Child in the Woods* that sparked the No Child Left Inside movement, as a nature-deficit disorder.

At the same time, climate change has led to biodiversity loss and has contributed to changes in weather and climate extremes from heatwaves to droughts. The environmental crisis makes the issue of the disconnection between humans and nature even more pertinent. Without opportunities to interact with nature, children are unable to forge deeper connections with the natural world, leading to indifference and unwillingness to protect it and thus further environmental deterioration. As children spend an increasing amount of time at school, education can be an important place where they come in contact with nature. However, many aspects of a typical educational environment nowadays are far from natural. Schools are almost entirely artificial structures made of concrete, with not a piece of grassland in sight. To address climate change and the continued loss of natural habitat and species in a meaningful way, students must be allowed to spend time in nature and away from the usual artificial surroundings. According to Hung (2008), our current environmental problems are linked to a negative understanding of nature as tame, domesticated, passive, subordinate, and completely separated and different from humankind. Introducing nature as a crucial part of the educational environment can help build a more harmonious relationship between humankind and nature by offering an alternative understanding of education and the world. Furthermore, as climate change increases the risk of pandemics and infectious diseases such as Covid-19, it can also prevent disruptions to education.

This article begins with an overview of the historic role of nature in education and the different purposes it has served over the centuries. It then discusses the rights-based approach to education and the link between human rights and nature. Finally, it proposes a modified human rights-based framework to education that incorporates nature as an integral part and it explores how learning in nature can

contribute to upholding human rights, on the one hand, and to connecting with nature and better protecting the fundamental rights of nature, on the other hand.

The role of nature in education: from a hygienic to a spiritual purpose

From Rousseau to Pestalozzi, some of the most renowned education reformers have highlighted the importance of nature. Froebel, a keen horticulturalist who would later introduce the concept of kindergarten or garden of children, championed planting and horticulture as one of the main activities in early childhood education (Fisher, 2018). In the late 19th century, Hermann Lietz introduced rural boarding schools or *Landerziehungsheim* for middle-class children in Ilsenburg in the Harz mountains which stressed the development of a childhood bond with nature (Chatelet, 2008).

In Spain, the founder of the Free Institution of Education, Francisco Giner de los Ríos (1884), criticized the practice of students staying indoors for hours on end and argued that schools had to have a field nearby for both pedagogical and hygienic reasons. Furthermore, Giner de los Ríos (1889) promoted the love of nature as one of the main psycho-physical or spiritual qualities of physical education. His disciple Cossío (2014) talked about introducing a focus on nature and bringing schools as close as possible to Rousseau's ideal school under a tree. The Free Institution of Education was dedicated to bringing students closer to nature and its educational programme was established around three main pillars: intense intellectual work, physical play outdoors and frequent exposure to nature and art (Sánchez, 2000). The Free Institution of Education was also linked to the introduction of excursions and summer camps in Spain. Excursions were introduced in 1878 after a visit to the Paris Exposition Universelle by Rafael Torres Campos, a historian and geographer at the Free Institution of Education, and were later promoted by Cossío (Sánchez, 2000). By 1884, papers

from abroad were reporting that the Free Institution of Education was using excursions more than any other educational institution in Europe (Pedrera, 2011). Apart from having pedagogical and social objectives, as they aimed to cultivate certain social and moral values ranging from fair play to cooperation and taking initiative (Urtaza, 1994), excursions also served hygienic purposes (Pedrera, 2011). They coincided with the spread of the hygienist movement at the end of the 19th and beginning of the 20th centuries, which aimed to mitigate the negative effects of the Industrial Revolution such as low wages, long working hours, overcrowded and unhealthy living conditions, and the spread of infectious diseases, and to create a healthier working class that would not depend so much on the ruling class by introducing public health policies, establishing professional associations, holding congresses, and modernizing education (Martínez, 2006). By 1885, there had been four outbreaks of cholera in Spain that century. The increase in the spread of diseases and the growing poverty affected disproportionately the lower social classes. Thus, many of the new educational reforms, especially the summer camps, were aimed at these classes as a way of tackling poverty and social exclusion and improving lives (Urtaza, 1994).

In the early 20th century, the focus on the hygienic and medical purpose of nature as an educational resource increased and the 1900s and 1910s saw the opening of the first forest schools or open-air schools to tackle diseases such as tuberculosis. The first open-air school opened in 1904 in Berlin. Established for working-class children, the Waldeschule of Charlottenburg was based on research into workers' living conditions and open-air cure stations and was situated in the heart of a forest, with sprawling grounds, gardens, sunbathing areas, and no asphalted surfaces (Chatelet, 2008). Open-air schools stressed out-of-school activities, gardening, bee-keeping, nature study, practical geography, dancing, and games (Cruickshank, 1977).

As tuberculosis and transmittable diseases were a problem throughout Europe, the schools quickly spread to other countries. Promoted by the Prussian government at international conferences in Nuremberg, London, Paris, and Buffalo, they soon sparked a movement (Chatelet, 2008). In Spain, they were established under the name *escuelas del bosque*. They were introduced by Domingo Barnés, a member of the Free Institution of Education, who after visiting the Franco-British Exhibition in London produced a report recommending the creation of open-air schools (Méndez, 2003). The first such schools included one in Montjuic, Barcelona, in 1914 and one in Dehesa de la Villa in Madrid in 1918. In 1922, an *escuela del mar* or sea school opened in Barcelona in a converted spa (Méndez, 2003). However, the discovery of penicillin at the end of WWII made open-air schools obsolete, with many closing or repurposed into institutions for students with disabilities.

Other initiatives attempting to incorporate nature and the outdoors in education in the early 20th century, such as Baden-Powell's Boy Scout movement or Kurt Hahn's Gordonstoun, while also focusing on improving health, mostly stressed character building, war fitness and readiness, and ameliorating social problems, especially juvenile delinquency (Cook, 1999). Again, these initiatives were mostly linked with the lower social classes.

It is not until the 1950s that the hygienic, medical, and social purposes of incorporating nature into education give way to a more philosophical or spiritual purpose. The shift towards a stronger emphasis on a closer and deeper connection with nature is linked with the appearance of forest kindergartens in Denmark. The first record of a Danish forest kindergarten can be traced back to 1952, when Ella Flatau, a Danish parent, took her children for a walk through the forest sparking an interest in an alternative type of education situated in nature (Bentsen et al., 2009). Today, forest

schools are defined as ‘a form of outdoor education that is particularly associated with Early Years education (children from the age of three to the age of eight) wherein young children spend time in forest or woodland settings’ (Leather, 2018, p. 6). Knight (2013) distinguishes several characteristics of forest schools: the setting is a forest or outdoor area; the setting is as safe as possible but allows risk-taking; it happens over time and children need to spend prolonged periods of time outdoors; it does not depend on the weather; it is based on trust; learning is play-based, child-initiated, and child-led; the day is divided into blocks and sessions; and the staff are specially trained. The Forest School Association (FSA) added another characteristic: a focus on holistic development that fosters resilient, independent, and creative learners (FSA, n.d.). Moreover, an especially important characteristic of the forest schools is the Scandinavian philosophy of *friluftsliv*. Found throughout Scandinavia, especially Norway and Sweden, the philosophy highlights experiences of freedom in nature, a spiritual connectedness with nature and the landscape, being and learning with nature and the land that leads to spiritual wholeness, and is strongly linked to Indigenous traditions (Leather, 2018). Since the 1950s, the idea has gained popularity and spread to other countries. However, authors have warned against the dilution of the forest school principal ideas outside of Scandinavia as *friluftsliv* is often not embraced as its underpinning philosophy and its methodology is increasingly commodified and commercialized in today’s neoliberal context (Leather, 2018).

The human rights-based approach to education

The United Nations, particularly UNESCO and UNICEF, have played an important role in introducing the rights-based approach to education. Since 1948 and the adoption of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, education has been recognized as a human

right. This has been reaffirmed in various international treaties such as the UNESCO Convention against Discrimination in Education (1960), the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (1966), the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (1981), and the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (1989). Initiatives such as the Education for All (EFA) movement, the Millennium Development Goals, the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, and Sustainable Development Goal 4, have also emphasized the right to education. Nevertheless, despite the focus on rights in international treaties and initiatives, education is increasingly conceptualized as human capital. The human rights-based approach to education appeared as an antidote to viewing education as human capital, prioritizing the intrinsic value of education over any instrumental value (Robeyns, 2006). In contrast to the human capital model of education, the rights-based approach upholds the view that all human beings are entitled to good quality education even in cases where their education is not likely to yield an economic return.

UNESCO's (2007) framework for the human rights-based approach to education entails three distinct dimensions: access to education, educational quality, and the environment in which education is provided. These three dimensions are interconnected and human rights in education can only be realized if all three dimensions are addressed. While the first two dimensions focus on education that is accessible, inclusive, student-centred, relevant, well-resourced, and well-monitored, the third dimension, the learning environment, focuses on meaningful participation, a violence-free environment, and respect for languages and cultures. The framework upholds a holistic approach to education that aims to ensure the universality and indivisibility of all human rights as well as tackle a range of challenges from poor quality of educational provision, exclusion, segregation, and violence, to child labor.

However, as climate change becomes an urgent threat in today's world, any holistic educational framework needs a strong focus on nature. For that purpose, I propose a modified human rights-based framework that incorporates nature as an integral part. On the one hand, learning in nature could uphold human rights, and, on the other hand, it could provide a way for humans to connect with nature and better protect the fundamental rights of nature.

Human rights and nature

The link between human rights and nature can be traced back to the late 1960s and early 1970s when the UN General Assembly decided to organize a conference on the human environment. The Declaration of the United Nations Conference on the Human Environment was adopted in 1972 at the conference. In the following decades, other important documents were adopted as well such as the 1982 World Charter for Nature, the 1992 Rio Declaration on Environment and Development, and the 1994 Draft Declaration of Human Rights and the Environment. Stipulating man's 'fundamental right to freedom, equality and adequate conditions of life, in an environment of a quality that permits a life of dignity and well-being', Principle 1 of the Declaration of the United Nations Conference on the Human Environment (1972) legally acknowledged the interdependence of human rights and the environment and started the debate on the need for upholding and protecting the human right to a safe, clean, healthy and sustainable environment. This right has still not been formally recognized. However, it is advocated by human rights and environmental organizations who recognize it is essential for the full enjoyment of a wide range of human rights such as the right to life, health, food, water and sanitation.

Nevertheless, this emphasis on the environment rather than nature has been

viewed by some critics as an anthropocentric approach that puts the human being at the centre of ecological issues and concerns (Handl, 2012). This approach began to change with the adoption of the Rio Declaration on Environment and Development which introduced the notion of living in harmony with nature, an idea that has been slowly gathering momentum. In 2009, the United Nations launched the Harmony with Nature initiative, resulting in the adoption of several resolutions and recent policy and legislation starting to recognize the rights of nature. Besides an increased focus on a more holistic approach, other significant developments in the field of human rights include expanding fundamental rights across species. Martha Nussbaum (2006) has argued against limiting fundamental rights and concepts such as law, justice, and entitlement to humans and expanding it to animals¹.

Learning in nature as a way to uphold human rights

Since the eradication of tuberculosis, the need for open-air therapy and improving students' health through fresh air, ventilation, and daily exposure to nature have been overlooked. Yet, the Covid-19 pandemic has demonstrated that the hygienic and medical purposes behind nature as an educational resource have not disappeared. The pandemic closed many schools around the world, and while many children were provided with online classes, still millions, especially the most vulnerable, were left with no access to education. Nevertheless, very few schools around the world responded by organizing classes outdoors. When it happened, outdoor classes were seen as the last resort in the face of internet blackouts and a lack of access to computers and

¹ Expanding fundamental rights across species is a highly debated and complex issue. Where we draw the line and whether we include all animals, plants, bacteria, and viruses depends on which ethical theory we invoke.

smartphones. Developing countries such as India reported using meadows, forests, orchards and fields as open-air classrooms to prevent students from dropping out after repeated lockdowns (Khan, 2020), or even painting murals on village walls and converting streets into makeshift classrooms (AFP, 2020). A Waldorf school in the US was one of the few that saw building open-air classrooms as a long-term investment and a way to promote a richer outdoor curriculum (Maine Coast Waldorf School, 2020). However, the possibility of future pandemics raises the need to question the current school environment. Incorporating nature in education would provide access to open spaces and fresh air, reducing the risk of the complete shut-down of educational institutions in the face of future challenges and thus upholding the human right to education.

Moreover, as the Incheon Declaration (2015) stipulated building and upgrading by 2030 ‘education facilities that are child, disability and gender sensitive and provide safe, non-violent, inclusive and effective learning environments for all’ (p. 74) as one of the indicators for ensuring inclusive and equitable quality education and promoting lifelong learning opportunities for all, we need to also question what a safe and effective learning environment entails. Often, schools have strong similarities with other institutional buildings and are characterized by sterile environments and very few natural elements. However, the benefits of nature for human beings have been widely recognized. A growing body of research demonstrates that exposure to nature is beneficial to mental wellbeing (Wang et al., 2019) and subjective wellbeing of adults (Carrus et al., 2015; Carrus et al., 2017). Adult’s exposure to nature has been associated with lower stress levels (Lega et al., 2021; Jiang et al., 2020) as well as lower depression and anxiety levels (Dzhambov et al., 2021). In Germany, Marselle et al. (2020) found that a higher street tree density is associated with lower antidepressant

prescription, particularly for people with low socioeconomic status. Exposure to nature has also been associated with better physical health and better overall health (Jiang et al., 2020). Similarly, studies focusing on children have found that exposure to nature improves children's wellbeing (Pirchio et al., 2021; Ward et al., 2016). Residential green spaces have shown a positive association with higher IQ of children living in urban areas (Bijnens et al., 2020). Outdoor classrooms have also been linked to an increased perception of wellbeing for both kindergarten students and teachers (Guardino et al., 2019). Furthermore, exposure to nature may promote learning via direct effects on students such as improving learners' attention, levels of stress, self-discipline, interest and enjoyment in learning, and physical activity, as well as by providing a calmer, quieter, safer, and more cooperative environment for learning (Kuo et al., 2019). Hence, more time spent outdoors during a school day could be a way not only to reduce the spread of infections, but it could also have many other positive benefits. Incorporating nature in education may create a learning environment that has the potential to improve human health, wellbeing, and learning which are integral for the enjoyment of a range of other human rights beyond the right to education and ensuring that human beings can fulfil their aspirations.

However, some authors have cautioned against our tendency to reduce nature to an object and protect it solely due to its instrumental role in connection to the wellbeing of human beings (Gianolla, 2013). This brings me to my second point: shifting the focus from human rights to the fundamental rights of nature.

Learning in nature as a way to connect with nature and better protect the fundamental rights of nature

Since Stone's (1972) article *Should Trees Have Standing – Toward Legal Rights for Natural Objects*, and later the work of Stutzin, Nash, Cullinan, and Berry, the idea that

nature has rights has slowly gained traction. It was not until the 2000s that the idea gained wider acceptance with Ecuador becoming the first country to recognize the rights of nature in its constitution. A few years later, New Zealand accorded legal personhood to Te Urewera. Nevertheless, Ecuador and New Zealand present two different cases of rights of nature with Ecuador's case concerning all of nature and giving specific rights, and New Zealand's concerning a particular entity and granting legal personhood (Tănăsescu, 2020). In short, the right of nature is a broad concept encompassing different aspects. From a philosophical aspect, it signifies a shift from an anthropocentric to an ecocentric attitude towards nature (Darpö, 2021).

This shift comes at a time when nature is suffering unprecedented changes produced by human activity and consumption. The 2018 Living Planet Report (World Wide Fund for Nature, 2018) found a 60% decline in animal population sizes since the 1970s, with South and Central America experiencing the most severe decline, 89%. There is mounting evidence that climate change is a serious threat to the wellbeing of humans and ecosystems. According to the IPCC (2021), human influence has warmed the climate at a record rate in the last 2000 years with human activity very likely the main driver of the global retreat of glaciers, the warming of the global upper ocean, the acidification of the surface open ocean, and the increase of the global mean sea level. Global warming is expected to increase climate-related risks to health, human security, livelihoods, food security, water supply, and economic growth (IPCC, 2018). To address environmental degradation and climate change, I argue that there needs to be not only a strong focus on nature in education but nature needs to form part of the educational environment.

Article 29 of the Convention on the Rights of the Child (1989) stipulates the development of respect for the natural environment through education. As children have

less direct contact and interactions with nature, it is crucial to provide them with access to nature and contact with nature on a regular basis. A modified human rights-based framework that incorporates nature as an integral part and allows us to rethink the school environment could enhance students' positive feelings toward nature and teach them not only to respect it but also to protect nature and the rights of nature. A growing body of research has found a positive relationship between spending time in nature and more pro-environmental behavior. Analysing data from a large, nationally representative survey of the adult population in England, Alcock et al. (2020) found that the more time individuals spend in nature and the more appreciation they have for the natural world, the more pro-environmental behavior they report. A large body of literature has increasingly focused on children and the effect of nature on children. Children's contact with nature has been found to enhance their pro-environmental attitude and behavior (Collado et al., 2013; Soga et al., 2016; Zhang et al., 2014). These studies have explored different types of contact with nature ranging from direct contact such as participating in nature-based activities, vicarious contact such as reading books, watching nature documentaries and programs, talking about nature with friends and family (Soga et al., 2016), and summer camps (Collado et al., 2013), to outdoor environmental education programs (Pirchio et al., 2021). Childhood experiences were also found to have a long-term effect as more contact with nature during childhood has been associated with more contact with nature as an adult, and this, in turn, has been positively associated with connectedness to nature and pro-environmental behavior (Rosa et al., 2018).

Hurly and Walker (2019) argued that connectedness with nature, the so-called nature relatedness defined by Nisbet et al. (2011) as 'the affective, cognitive, and experiential relationship individuals have with the natural world or a subjective sense of

connectedness with nature' (p. 304), should be considered a basic psychological need. Ever since the biologist E. O. Wilson proposed the biophilia hypothesis in the late 20th century, the idea of humans sharing an innate bond with the natural world rooted in tens of thousands of years of shared evolutionary history began to gain wide acceptance. This human 'innate tendency to focus on life and lifelike processes' (Wilson, 2003, p. 1) is what makes human beings unable to find meaning apart from the rest of the species on earth. Drawing on Wilson's work, the concept of ecophilia emerged in education. One of the first to introduce the concept, Sobel (1996) defined ecophilia as 'supporting children's biological tendency to bond with the natural world' (p. 6), as opposed to ecophobia or 'a fear of ecological problems and the natural world' (p. 5). Hung (2017) expanded the concept of ecophilia to include not only our affective bond with all living beings but also with all non-living beings within our surroundings and proposed it as a central concept for conceiving ecopedagogy, an ecological approach to education that serves as an antidote to the current model of education that pays little attention to nature and a way to reconnect 'humans and the environment in an ecologically meaningful way' (p. 43). In ecopedagogy, spending time in nature is crucial. Hung (2014) argues that the cultivation of knowledge about nature and the care for nature are emphasized. Only through personal direct experience of a place, in this case spending time in nature and with nature, can an authentic sense of place be created that humans experience as meaningful, valuable, and irreplaceable (Hung, 2014). Too often, environmental education takes place away from the natural habitat in classrooms where students are unable to form meaningful and profound experiences and where they are taught in very abstract ways. However, premature abstraction in education, especially when teaching abstract concepts like climate change, can be counterproductive and may result in ecophobia where children are unable to bond with the natural world (Sobel, 1996). For

ecophilia to take hold, human beings need to be given an opportunity and be encouraged to experience nature first-hand from an early age.

Nevertheless, direct experiences in nature are only the first step. For human beings to connect with nature and better protect it, we need to move away from the current anthropocentric approach. To do so, several authors have proposed drawing on the ways different cultures, especially Indigenous ones, value the natural world and nature. In regards to human rights, for example, Gianolla (2013) argued for the need to incorporate the cosmovision of the Indigenous peoples of Bolivia and Ecuador whose concept of good life recognizes the Earth as a living being.

Nature plays a crucial role in the belief systems of numerous cultures. In Japan, the Shinto religion maintains that nature is imbued with supernatural entities and is sacred. In Chinese traditional culture, *tien-rén-hé-yi* or the harmony between humanity and nature is a key concept (Hung, 2019). In the US, Native Americans' beliefs are rooted in ancestral places and the idea that human beings belong to the land and are related to all living things and as such are responsible for their health and survival (Chawla, 2021). As was discussed earlier in this article, we see that some of these beliefs are gaining wider acceptance in education such as the case of Scandinavia and the *friluftsliv* philosophy. As the anthropocentrism of the past century has coincided with unprecedented environmental degradation, an alternative approach based on Indigenous beliefs highlighting the harmonious and spiritual connection with nature could help us address our disconnection with the natural world and protect the fundamental rights of nature. However, given the long history of colonialization and appropriation of Indigenous philosophies and the fact that they are increasingly used to inform current Western scholarship, it is important to adopt respectful, ethical, and culturally appropriate practices that are not exploitative, that do not marginalize

Indigenous scholars but engage with them, and that draw on local Indigenous cultures where possible rather than assuming all Indigenous cultures are the same (See Todd, 2016; Tuhiwai Smith, 2008; Tuhiwai Smith et al., 2019).

Conclusion

The idea of incorporating nature in education is not new. While there have been various attempts in the past to take education out in the open for different reasons ranging from hygienic to spiritual, today nature still plays a small role. Yet, in the words of Kuo et al. (2019): ‘it is time to take nature seriously as a resource for learning and development’.

The Covid-19 pandemic highlighted the need for a paradigm shift in the way we understand the educational environment. Millions of children were deprived of access to education in what the UN called the largest disruption of education to date. With climate change and the loss of natural habitat likely to make us more vulnerable to future pandemics, incorporating nature in education can make us more resistant to shocks and can ensure the right to education and a range of other interrelated rights. Furthermore, by drawing on ecopedagogy and Indigenous beliefs underlining a harmonious relationship with nature, we can make sure that an amplified rights-based framework to education where nature plays an important part protects both human rights and the fundamental rights of nature.

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